

Groundwater Quality Dynamics from Field Experiments on Watershed Level in Southern Bulgaria.

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Abstract

The results of the groundwater dynamics are presented realized on the territory of a small watershed at the experimental station Tsalapitsa in South Bulgaria, under Fluvisol. The shallow waters of three permanent built wells from the experimental field were studied when growing different crops with different fertilization for the period 2016-2018. The samples for chemical analysis were taken monthly. It was found that different agricultural practices influenced significantly on the content and dynamics on nitrogen in the shallow groundwater. The highest concentration of nitrogen were measured when vegetables were grown, while at a change in the loading with fertilizers the values are lower around and below MPCL. The calcium concentrations of groundwater vary in considerably short range, such as correlates to a certain extent with the nitrate content.

Key words: groundwater, chemical composition, agriculture, fertilization

Introduction

Groundwater is one of the most valuable water resources. It is known that the protection of groundwater quality is actual problem not only for economic reasons, but also because of its great social significance. The conducted researches (Beaudoin et al., 2005; Stoicheva et al., 2013; Simeonova et al., 2015, 2017; Singh et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2013) in recent showed a significant load of surface and underground water with nitrogen and other nutrients in areas with improper fertilization, livestock farms and urban areas. The chemical composition of groundwater depends on natural factors (soil, geology, climate) and anthropogenic impact (fertilizers, irrigation, etc). Groundwater protection is of particular importance, as hydrological indicators show that water quality is slowly improving after changes in agricultural practice. It is known that studying of pathways and mechanisms for nutrients leaching out of the root zone and their downward movement through the intermediate vadose zone on a watershed level is a very difficult task, because of the hidden and complicated character of the processes. According to some authors the use of modeling approaches to study groundwater pollution or the interaction between surface water and groundwater has become a trend, but the accuracy of the modeling results greatly depends on the accuracy of the information and on the magnitude and distribution of aquifer permeability (Sanford, 2002; Piccini et al., 2016). The EU focuses on sustainable and environmentally

sound farming, by developing a thematic strategy on soil (European Commission, 2006 a, b) and water protection (Directive 91/676/EEC and Directive 2000/60/EEC).

The aim of this study is to present results on monitoring the dynamics of chemical elements in the shallow groundwater in a field experimental station on Fluvisol under conditions of changing anthropogenic loading.

Material and Methods

The field experiment is located in south Bulgaria (24035'E; 42014'N), near the city of Plovdiv in the village of Tsalapitsa. The region belongs to the transition subzone between Moderate and Mediterranean Continental climate zones. According to the classification of the country thermal conditions, the experimental area belongs to temperate hot and dry zone Levichanska (1991). The region is characterized with mean annual climatic data on: annual precipitation of 340 mm in 2016; 494,5 mm in 2017; and 482 mm in 2018. The average rainfall for this region of 500-540 mm. The average annual air temperature is 12.5-12.8 °C. The soil was classified as Alluvial-meadow soil Koynov (1987), which corresponds to Eutric Fluvisol in FAO classification (FAO, WRBSR, 2015). The hydrogeological research on the territory shows high spatial heterogeneity of the thickness and distribution of the alluvial materials (Stoichev et al., 1980; Mateva et al., 1982). The sandy clay loam soil has AC type of profile and a high infiltration rate and permeability. The depth of groundwater level varies between 2.6 and 4.8 m. (during the period of research varied to 5.9 m) The soil profile has coarse texture, low water holding capacity and conditions for fast water movement downward the profile, which is a precondition for migration of the dissolved materials through the soil profile. The arable horizon has the following mean characteristics: light texture, low clay content, bulk density between 1.54 and 1.66 g.cm⁻³, pH_{H2O} is 6.0 – 6.5, low humus and total nitrogen content, respectively 0.70% and 0.052 %, low cation exchange capacity in the plough soil layer total. The physico-chemical properties of the soil are presented in Table 1. Fluctuation of the shallow groundwater table was monitored at three (№ 5, 6, 7) permanent wells (Ø 220 mm) and samples for chemical analysis were taken monthly. The assessment of groundwater chemical composition was based on data for the period of 2016-2018, where different agricultural crops were grown which are fertilized with different N-rates on the background of the phosphorus and potassium. The pH values and chemical elements (K⁺, Na⁺, Ca²⁺, NO₃⁻, HCO₃⁻, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻) of groundwater samples are determined using the laboratory methods of analysis described in Arinushkina (1970) and Page et al., (1982).

Table 1. Characteristics of the studied Fluvisol

Horizons	Depth, cm	pH _{H2O}	Humus %	Total			Sorption capacity, meq.100g ⁻¹	Particle size, mm		
				N, %	C:N	CaCO ₃ , %		0.02-0.002 %	0.002 %	< 0.002 %
Alluvial-meadow soil - Fluvisol										
A _{arable}	0-35	6.0	0.70	0.052	7.8	0.00	7.92	66.3	16.2	17.5
A ₂	35-60	6.4	0.55	0.050	6.4	0.00	18.18	43.4	14.8	41.8
A ₃ C ₁	60-87	6.5	0.42	0.042	5.8	0.00	22.77	33.5	20.6	45,9
C ₂	87-118	6.5	0.38	0.030	7.5	0.00	23.11	31.4	29.6	39.0

According to D.Stoichev, 1997.

Results and Discussion

Data on groundwater table fluctuation during the monitoring period are presented in Table 2. The dynamics of the groundwater table detected during the monitoring period follows the seasonal distribution of the precipitation. The variation of the average amount of precipitation during the studied period reach to 100 mm. The data show that spring-summer and autumn maximums of precipitation were observed.

Fig. 1. Monthly precipitation sums for the periods 2016-2018 in Tsalapitsa, South Bulgaria.

The highest water table fluctuation was observed in monitoring well №6 during the whole studied period.

Table 2. Depth of groundwater table (wells № 5,6,7) in the experimental field Tsalapitsa, the period (2016-2018).

Depth,m	No of wells		
	5	6	7
Min	4.4	4.7	4.0
Max	5.6	5.9	5.0
Mean \pm Stdv	5.07 \pm 0.25	5.28 \pm 0.29	4.53 \pm 0.20

The groundwater samples obtained from the three monitoring wells have neutral to alkaline reaction throughout the study period (Figure 2). Fluctuation of the pH values in the three wells is almost the same. Two deviations were observed, one in March 2016 when the pH in well № 5 (pH 6.9) was the lowest compared to the other wells and the other in November 2020, when the measured pH 8,60 in well № 6 was higher than in the other two wells. These differences are statistically not significant. No seasonality was found on the pH values .

Fig. 2. pH of groundwater in the experimental field Tsalapitsa, during the period (2016-2018).

Table 3. Chemical composition (mg.l^{-1}) of the studied wells in the experimental field Tsalapitsa during the period (2016-2018).

Elements, mg.l^{-1}	No of wells		
	5	6	7
K+			
Min	0.22	0.33	0.16
Max	1.68	5.01	2.01
Mean \pm Stdv	0.83 \pm 0.39	1.42 \pm 0.43	0.82 \pm 0.48
Na+			
Min	25.72	22.98	19.63
Max	45.00	50.78	41.64
Mean \pm Stdv	31.76 \pm 5.15	29.37 \pm 6.08	26.79 \pm 4.83
Ca ²⁺			
Min	32.50	29.50	28.00
Max	93.40	91.50	77.50
Mean \pm Stdv	69.82 \pm 17.23	64.9 \pm 16.09	56.83 \pm 12.88
NO ₃ ⁻			
Min	12.73	10.43	4.40
Max	68.70	43.20	34.40
Mean \pm Stdv	35.71 \pm 13.42	26.2 \pm 6.81	17.89 \pm 7.32
HCO ₃ ⁻			
Min	172.08	190.00	198.62
Max	358.04	414.38	358.05
Mean \pm Stdv	307.95 \pm 36.65	270.83 \pm 42.26	299.20 \pm 36.02
Cl ⁻			
Min	6.13	5.00	6.70
Max	15.10	21.00	13.90
Mean \pm Stdv	10.66 \pm 2.19	13.79 \pm 3.06	10.00 \pm 1.98
SO ₄ ²⁻			
Min	79.00	67.00	58.00
Max	140.00	150.00	122.00
Mean \pm Stdv	104.6 \pm 15.23	95.63 \pm 18.47	89.97 \pm 18.26

On Figure 3, the dynamics in the K^+ content in the groundwater is presented. In general, potassium is an element, which is characterized with very low mobility coefficient. It is subject to physico-chemical fixation.

Fig. 3. Dynamic of potassium content in groundwater in the experimental field Tsalapitsa, during the period (2016-2018).

The highest of K^+ content was observed in the well No 6, which is close to the long-term fertilizer experiment. Potassium content varies from 0.16 to 5.02 mg.l-1 (Table 3), while the lowest values was measured in the summer months of 2016 and the spring months of 2018 at all three wells.

The dynamics of sodium in groundwater (Figure 4) from all studied wells follows almost the same trend of changes over time. Sodium as compared to potassium has higher values in the groundwater (19.63-50.78 mg.l⁻¹). Sodium is an element with high geochemical mobility and transitional status in the geochemical cycle and due to this reason it is highly influenced by the changing anthropogenic loads. (change in fertilizer rates, reduced water available to move around the profile, and cultivated crops (cereals without irrigation).

Fig. 4. Dynamic of sodium content in groundwater in the experimental field Tsalapitsa, during the period (2016-2018).

As it is shown on Table 3, calcium concentrations in groundwater varies from 28.0 to 93.4 mg.l⁻¹, which is not typical for this element due to its high mobility and status in the geochemical cycle of elements. Similar behavior of calcium was found in a study by Stoicheva et al., (2013).

Fig. 5. Dynamic of calcium in groundwater in the experimental field Tsalapitsa, during the period (2016-2018).

Although the variation is not so big, its temporal pattern seems to follow that of the nitrate content. Calcium concentrations for the study period did not exceed the MPCL for drinking water (150 mg.l⁻¹).

Fig. 6. Dynamic of nitrate content in groundwater in the experimental field Tsalapitsa, during the period (2016-2018).

In their study Li P et al., (2013 a,b) found that, mineral weathering (carbonate and silicate minerals) and ion exchange are the most important factors controlling groundwater chemistry. Nitrogen distribution assessment on a watershed level is usually difficult because of lack of information for the vadose zone, the uncertainties of nitrogen input and soil and landscape diversity. Data on nitrate content for the periods 2016-2018 (Figure 6) confirm the tendency of decreasing nitrate concentration compared to previous study periods in the

experimental field Stoicheva et al., (2013). The average values of nitrates around and below the maximum permitted contamination are observed. But there are peak values of nitrate during spring-autumn months. The highest concentrations of nitrate in monitoring wells N5 were registered in February 2016 and November 2018.

Fluctuation in the nitrate concentrations varied in a range of 20-45 mg.l⁻¹. However, the absolute values in the three wells were different. The lowest nitrate concentration – 4.40 mg.l⁻¹ in average was measured in the samples taken from monitoring well № 7 and the highest – 68.70 mg.l⁻¹ in average in well № 5.

Fig. 7. Dynamic of hydro-carbonates content in groundwater in the experimental field Tsalapitsa, during the period (2016-2018).

The coefficient of variation reaches to 45 % (at $p \leq 0.05$), the highest being in well 7. The coefficient of variation is similar for potassium also in well 7 which indicates that the variation in these elements under this particular soil have one and the same origin.

The concentrations of hydro-carbonates range from 172.08 to 414.38 mg.l⁻¹ was detected (Figure 7), such as the highest values are found in well № 6. The data do not show any spatial or temporal dependence from other measured concentrations. Chlorine content in the groundwater could be characterised with considerably low variation in space and time. (Figure 7). His behavior is almost the same as for calcium concentrations. The data have a narrow range (5.0-21.0 mg.l⁻¹), which is not typical for this element due to its high mobility and in the geochemical cycle.

The highest Cl content was observed in May 2018. The anthropogenic loads strengthened the dynamics of chlorine in groundwater because of the absence of mechanisms in the soil to adsorb chlorine from drainage water. Chlorine, like sodium, has a transitional status in the biological turnover of nutrients. The data show (Table 3), that the sulfates concentrations vary from 58.0 to 150 mg.l⁻¹, with the highest values are found in the well n 6.

Fig. 8. Dynamic of chlorine content in groundwater in the experimental field Tsalapitsa, during the period (2016-2018).

Fig. 9. Dynamic of sulphates content in groundwater in the experimental field Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv region during the period (2016-2018).

Conclusion

It was established that groundwater samples in the studied watershed has neutral to alkaline reaction and hydrocarbonate-calcium composition. It was found that fluctuations in the three wells levels are similar. Correlation between the dynamics of potassium and nitrate contents was recognized which indicate that temporal fluctuation should have the same origin. The calcium concentrations in groundwater do not exceed the maximum permissible contaminate level for drinking water and its fluctuation corresponds to that of the nitrate content. Nitrate content in the groundwater was influenced by the anthropogenic loads and a decreasing trend in nitrate concentration was observed when fertilization is reduced. It was monitored a significant variation in the data for hydro-carbonates content in the groundwater, slightly influenced by the anthropogenic loading. Chlorine and sulphate contents in the groundwater could be characterised with lower variation. A similar coefficient of variation was found for both elements respectively ($C_v = 14$ to 22% at $p \leq 0.05$).

As a general conclusion, the intensive agricultural activity of alluvial-meadow soil creates conditions for more dynamic water movement through the soil profile and migration of some chemical elements.

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